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INSIDER TRADING: A CASE STUDY OF LARSEN & TOUBRO AND DLF

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ABSTRACT

Insider Trading can simply be defined as Trading in the shares of a company by the person who are in the management of the company or are close to them on the basis of undisclosed price sensitive information regarding the working of the company, which they possess but which is not available to others. In the present Research Paper we tried to understand the phases of Insider trading laws in India and its legal framework considering the case study L&T and DLF. After analyzing the legal Framework of insider Trading we concluded that there have been a lot of laws, protecting the interests of investors as we have seen how the laws came into being right from The Thomas Committee Report in 1948 to now SEBI becoming the watchdog of the financial markets. Every phase helped in overcoming the drawbacks of the previous laws which were being used by companies to help them in insider trading.

Key Words: Trading, Insider Trading, SEBI, DLF, Investor

Introduction: Insider trading is a crime on the faith of fair dealing in the capital market. The stringency and scope of violation and penalty differs from country to country. Trading in shares of the company by an insider is violation of law. For example, an insider may come across a corporate fraud and disclose the fraud. An insider can also create information according to his future actions.

Trading by insiders, like directors, officers and employees of the company in the shares of their own company is actually a positive feature, and companies should encourage it as this aligns its interests with those of the insiders.

What actually is prohibited is the trading by an insider in breach of a duty of confidence in the stock of a company on the basis of non-public information to the exclusion of others. If insider trading is allowed unregulated the vast majority of investors will lose interest in the securities market. Therefore the governing bodies play an important role in protecting the interests of the investors and allowing enough funds for the companies

The objectives of the study are as under:

- To explain the concept of insider trading
- To study the rules and regulations under SEBI([Prohibition of] Insider Trading) Regulations, 1992
- To understand the phases of insider trading laws in India
- To study the rules and regulations of as laid down under the Companies Act,2013 regarding Insider Trading
- To study various companies held for insider trading and the legal proceedings against them
- To study the concept of legal insider trading

Research being a part of literature review is based on secondary source of information. Besides internet various sources like Companies Act 2013, SEBI guidelines, etc were used.

The study has been divided in seven sections. The first section is a mere introduction to the whole research. The second section talks about the conceptual framework which lists down the definitions given by various research

scholars. The next section traces the phases by which insider trading laws have come into picture. Legal framework i.e. The Companies Act 2013 and SEBI guidelines relating to insider trading form the next section. The fifth section tells about the companies held guilty for insider trading. Lastly we come to the conclusion of the whole research in the end.

The *Patel Committee* in India in 1986 defined insider trading as “the trading in the shares of a company by the person who are in the management of the company or are close to them on the basis of undisclosed “*price sensitive information*” regarding the working of the company, which they possess but which is not available to others”(Associates, 2014)

SEBI had amended the definition of ‘insider’ under Regulation 2(e) in 2008 vide the SEBI (Prohibition of Insider Trading) (Amendment) Regulations, 2008. In the present statute, Regulation 2(e) of SEBI ([Prohibition of] Insider Trading) Regulations, 1992 defines an “insider” as any person who,

- is or was connected with the company or is deemed to have been connected with the company and is reasonably expected to have access to unpublished price sensitive information in respect of securities of a company, or,
- has received or has had access to such unpublished price sensitive information.

Trading which is generally read under the wide ambit of dealing in securities has been defined under Regulation 2(d) which says “dealing in securities” means an act of subscribing, buying, selling or agreeing to subscribe, buy, sell or deal in any securities by any person either as principal or agent.(SEBI([Prohibition Of] Insider Trading) Regulations, 1992)

Finally, in terms of definitions, the *Justice Sodhi Committee* seeks to clearly define the expression “trading” in order to distinguish it from the wider expression “dealing”. “Trading” means the acquisition and disposal of securities. Hence, creating a security over the shares of a company would not amount to “trading” in those securities.(Insider Trading Investopedia)

The rationale behind the prohibition of insider trading is “the obvious need and understandable concern about the damage to public confidence which insider dealing is likely to cause and the clear intention to prevent, so far as possible, what amounts to cheating when those with inside knowledge use that knowledge to make a profit in their dealings with others.”(Attorney General's Reference No.1, 1988)

Legal Insider Trading

Legal trading by insiders is common as employees of companies having public subscription often have stock or options. This has been made public in United States by Securities Exchange Commission.

Arguments for legalizing Insider Trading

Some of the economists and legal scholars have been arguing that there should not be any laws against insider trading. They believe that material nonpublic information actually benefits the investors by quickly circulating new information.

Friedman, laureate of the Nobel Memorial Prize in Economics, said: "You want more insider trading, not less. You want to give the people most likely to have knowledge about deficiencies of the company an incentive to make the public aware of that." He believed that buying and selling created pressure in the market.

Some argue that insider trading does not victimize investors. They believe it is an act of transferring property without a contract where the willing seller rightfully owns the property. The Atlantic has described the process as "arguably the closest thing that modern finance has to a victimless crime".

Some advocates of legalization argue that conveying material information which may affect the stock price is similar to right of free speech unless the insider has promised not to disclose or if it is some sensitive information like bank passwords.

PHASES OF INSIDER TRADING LAWS IN INDIA

The entire debate on the intricacies of insider trading dwindles in between two extreme comments; one remark by a former president of the Bombay Stock Exchange in 1992 stating that "*There is no other kind of trading in India, but the insider variety*", and the statement by Mr. Arthur Levitt, the then Securities Exchange Commission Chairman in 1998, "*Insider trading has utterly no place in any fair-minded law-abiding economy*".

India's encounter with insider trading was first seen in the 1940s. The *Thomas Committee Report* in 1948 cited instances of directors, agents, officers, auditors possessing strategic information regarding economic conditions of the company regarding the size of the dividends to be declared, or of the issue of bonus shares or the awaiting conclusion of a favorable contract prior to public disclosure.

Thus, Sections 307 and 308 were incorporated in the Companies Act of 1956. Section 307 provided for maintenance of a register by the companies to record the directors' shareholdings in the company. Section 308 prescribed to the duty of the directors and persons deemed to be the directors to make disclosure of their shareholdings in the company. Thereafter, by the Companies Amendment Act, 1960 had extended this requirement to the shareholdings of a company's managers as well. However, these provisions could not curb this practice of insider trading due to which the directors or managing agents making unfair use of inside information could go scot free. The absence of specific regulations in this aspect despite the recommendations of the *Thomas Committee* was a major deterrent.

In 1979, the *Sachar Committee* said in its report that directors, auditors, company secretaries etc. may have some price sensitive information that could be used to manipulate stock prices which may cause financial misfortunes to the investing public. The companies recommended amendments to Companies Act 1956 to restrict or prohibit the dealings of the employees. This Committee opined that Sections 307 and 308 of the Companies Act were insufficient to curb insider trading.

The *Patel Committee* in 1986 defined Insider Trading as "*Trading in the shares of a company by the person who are in the management of the company or are close to them on the basis of undisclosed price sensitive information regarding the working of the company, which they possess but which is not available to others*". The *Patel Committee* also recommended that the Securities Contract (Regulation) Act, 1956 may be amended to make exchanges curb insider trading and unfair insider trading and unfair stock deals. Section 21 of the SCRA mandated compliance of the conditions prescribed under the listing agreement between the company and the stock exchange. Each stock exchange can formulate its own terms and conditions of the listing agreement.

The *Abid Hussain Committee* in 1989 recommended that insider trading be convicted under civil and criminal laws and also that SEBI formulate the regulation and governing codes to prevent unfair deals.

The recommendations of the various committees and the needs of rapidly advancing securities market gave way to the formulation of a comprehensive legislation known as the SEBI (Insider Trading) Regulations, 1992 which after subsequent amendment in 2002 to plug certain loopholes revealed in the cases of *Hindustan Lever Ltd. v. SEBI*[8] and *Rakesh Agarwal v. SEBI*[9], came to be known as SEBI ([Prohibition of] Insider Trading) Regulations, 1992 and which prohibited fraudulent practice and a person involved in insider trading to be held guilty for such malpractice.

Recently, the SEBI panel in 2013, headed by former Chief justice of India N. K. Sodhi suggested that trades by promoters, employees, directors and their immediate relatives would need to be disclosed internally to the company. The *Justice Sodhi Committee* on Insider Trading Regulations made a range of recommendations to the legal framework for prohibition of insider trading in India and focused on making this area of regulation more predictable, precise and clear by suggesting a combination of principles-based regulations and rules that are backed by principles. The Committee also suggested that each regulatory provision may be backed by a note on legislative intent.

As on date, SEBI, the market watchdog, regulates insider trading through the SEBI Act and the Insider Trading Regulations.

LEGAL FRAMEWORK OF INSIDER TRADING

The Securities and Exchange Board of India

The Securities and Exchange Board of India, (“SEBI”), by powers vested on it through Section 30 of the Securities and Exchange Board of India Act, 1992, has come up with the Securities and Exchange Board (Prohibition of Insider Trading) Regulations, 1992, emphasizing on the prohibition on dealing, communicating or counseling on matters relating to insider trading.

The provision clearly states that no insider shall—

- either on his own behalf or on behalf of any other person, deal in securities of a company listed on any stock exchange when in possession of any unpublished price sensitive information; or,
- communicate or counsel or procure directly or indirectly any unpublished price sensitive information to any person who while in possession of such unpublished price sensitive information shall not deal in securities:

Provided that, nothing contained above shall be applicable to any communication required in the ordinary course of business or profession or employment or under any law.

The provision also states that no company shall deal in the securities of another company or associate of that other company while in possession of any unpublished price sensitive information. Any insider who deals in securities in contravention of the provisions of regulation 3 or 3A shall be guilty of insider trading. The power of investigation vests with the Board, which can elect one or a number of members to look into the book of accounts and take *suo moto* cognizance of any complaint received on behalf of or against an insider.

All listed companies and organizations associated with securities market, including other intermediaries, are mandated to frame a code of internal procedures and conduct in correspondence to the *Model Code*.

The Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI) has notified the SEBI (Prohibition of Insider Trading) Regulations, 2015 on 15th January, 2015.

The new Regulations chalk out a stricter and more focused regulatory regime and have put in place a stronger legal and enforcement framework for prevention of Insider Trading. The penalties imposed under the Companies Act, 2013 and the SEBI Act, 1992 for non-compliance and contravention of these Regulations are huge. The new Regulations have been uploaded on the MMFSL intranet portal.

Following are the important provisions of the Regulations:

- There shall be prohibition on all designated persons for exercise of ESOPs during the trading window closure period and there shall be prohibition on all designated persons for exercise of ESOPs for six months after sale of shares, and vice versa.
- There shall be no contra trade even in case of ESOP.
- The Regulations prescribe that every employee shall disclose to the Company details of the trade within 2 trading days of the transaction, if the value of securities traded in one or a series of transactions in any calendar quarter exceeds Rs.10 lakhs. The disclosures shall include those relating to trading by immediate relatives and by any other person for whom the trading decisions are taken.
- A designated person who buys or sells any number of securities of the company shall not enter into an opposite transaction i.e. sell or buy respectively any number of securities of the Company during the next six months following the prior transaction.
- A new concept of trading plans has been introduced in India for an insider under the Regulations.
- If any Designated Person or his/her immediate relative(s) intend(s) to trade in securities exceeding market value of Rs.42 lakhs during a calendar month, then he/she should apply to the Compliance Officer for pre-clearance, even during the period when the window is open.
- The trading window shall be closed for adopting and considering financial results and other Unpublished Price Sensitive Information matters.

The trading window shall be closed when the Compliance Officer determines that a designated person or class of designated persons can reasonably be expected to have possession of unpublished price sensitive information. Moreover, the designated persons and their immediate relatives shall not trade in securities when the trading window is closed. (SEBI (Prohibition of Insider Trading) Regulations 2015)

Companies Act, 2013

Section 195 of the Companies Act 2013 prohibits insider trading. As per Section 195 of the Companies Act 2013:

(1) No person including any director or key managerial personnel of a company shall enter into insider trading:

Provided that nothing contained in this sub-section shall apply to any communication required in the ordinary course of business or profession or employment or under any law.

Explanation.—for the purposes of this section,—

(a) “Insider trading” means—

(i) an act of subscribing, buying, selling, dealing or agreeing to subscribe, buy, sell or deal in any securities by any director or key managerial personnel or any other officer of a company either as principal or agent if such director or key managerial personnel or any other officer of the company is reasonably expected to have access to any non-public price sensitive information in respect of securities of company; or

(ii) an act of counselling about procuring or communicating directly or indirectly any non-public price-sensitive information to any person;

(b) “price-sensitive information” means any information which relates, directly or indirectly, to a company and which if published is likely to materially affect the price of securities of the company.

COMPANIES HELD FOR INSIDER TRADING

1. DLF

Background

DLF had filed a draft red herring prospectus with SEBI in January 2007 for raising Rs.9187.5 crore through an IPO. Thereafter, DLF issued the prospectus on May 25, 2007 and it was filed with the Registrar of Companies on June 18, 2007. One Mr. Kimsuk Sinha had filed complaints with SEBI on June 4, 2007 alleging the Sudipti Estates Private Limited and certain other persons had defrauded him of 34 crore in relation to a transaction between them for purchase of land ("Complaint") and also registered a first information report dated April 26, 2007 alleging that two of DLF's wholly owned subsidiaries were the only shareholders of the Sudipti and requesting to disallow the listing of DLF pursuant to the IPO and for immediate action. Subsequently the allegations in Complaint were denied by DLF.

SEBI's investigation in pursuance of Delhi High Court's order

Due to inaction of SEBI of the complaint against DLF, a Writ Petition was filed by Mr. Sinha before the Delhi High Court and it issued directions to SEBI for undertaking an investigation into the complaints. Accordingly SEBI ordered an investigation into the allegations to ascertain the violations, if any, of the provisions of the DIP Guidelines and corresponding provisions of ICDR Regulations and the Companies Act, 1956 and issued a Show Cause Notice to the Noticees.

Charges levied by SEBI

1. Nondisclosure of material information in relation to alleged subsidiaries by DLF in Prospectus

At that time, 3 wholly owned subsidiaries held the entire equity shares in Sudipti, Shalika Estate Developers Pvt Ltd and Felicite Builders & Construction Pvt. Ltd. The entire shareholding in Felicite held by the wholly owned subsidiary was sold to 3 people who were wives of key managerial personnel of DLF. The wholly owned subsidiary sold the entire shareholding in Shalika to Felicite on November 30, 2006 and the 3 wholly owned subsidiaries of DLF sold their entire shareholding in Sudipti to Shalika. The said wives were shareholders of Felicite till their husbands were KMPs and when they ceased to be the KMPs, shares were transferred to other KMPs' wives. Also payments in respect of those transfers were made by the respective husbands of the purchasers. Hence SEBI alleged that DLF never lost control of Sudipti, Shalika and Felicite and they remained the subsidiaries of DLF. In terms of the provisions of DIP Guidelines and AS-23, certain disclosures with respect to its subsidiaries should have been disclosed in the Prospectus of DLF but was not disclosed. Therefore, it was held that DLF has violated provisions of the DIP Guidelines.

2. Non-disclosure of related party transactions by DLF in Prospectus

There was no change in board of members in the subsidiaries. They were also the employees of DLF and they continued to be the directors of the subsidiaries even after the sale of shareholding. There was no change in the authorized signatories of bank accounts, registered office and the statutory auditors of subsidiaries even after the date of dissociation. Hence, SEBI inferred that DLF was in a position to control the boards and its employees were involved in day-to-day operations. They were associated with subsidiaries even after they claimed to be dissociated. Therefore, the subsidiaries were related parties of DLF as per AS-18. Hence, SEBI held that DLF had failed to disclose its related party transactions.

3. *Non-disclosure of outstanding litigation relating to Alleged Subsidiaries by DLF in Prospectus*
Further, the DIP Guidelines required DLF to disclose outstanding litigation in respect of its subsidiaries or any other litigations whose outcome could have a materially adverse effect on the financial position of DLF. However, the Prospectus of DLF did not provide any information of the FIR.
4. *Violations of DIP guidelines by five directors and CFO of DLF*
Since the directors and CFO of DLF had authorised the Prospectus and signed the declarations certifying the compliance with DIP Guidelines, SEBI held that they have failed to ensure disclosures to be true and correct thereby violating provisions of DIP guidelines.
5. *Deliberate and active suppression of material information amounting to Fraud in terms of Prohibition of Fraudulent and Unfair Trade Practices relating to Securities Market*
In compilation of all the aforesaid facts, SEBI held that the entire share transfer process in the subsidiaries was executed through sham transactions by DLF and its subsidiaries by camouflaging the association of *Sudipti* with DLF as dissociation thereby failing to ensure disclosures of subsidiaries. (DLF Case summary)

Larsen and Toubro

Background

At least 70 entities including FIIs, foreign brokerage firms and others were under scanner for suspected insider trading activities and circulation of 'unpublished price sensitive information' for unfair trade practices. The probe against these entities follows unearthing of a major insider trading case in shares of L&T Finance, in which capital markets regulator SEBI barred a Cayman Islands-based hedge fund and Factorial Master Fund from Indian securities markets.

The fund, managed by Hong Kong based Factorial Capital Management, traded in derivative contracts of L&T Finance with Offshore Derivative Contracts through five different Foreign Institutional Investors in an "aberrant and suspicious" manner. These five FIIs were Macquarie Bank, Goldman Sachs Singapore, Merrill Lynch CM Espana, Nomura Singapore and Citigroup Global Markets Mauritius Ltd. A probe by the capital markets regulator found that the Factorial was involved as potential investor in the market gauging exercise undertaken by Credit Suisse as 'Seller Broker' of L&T Finance for its Offer for Sale in March.

SEBI had passed an interim order barring Factorial from Indian markets. When contacted Credit Suisse spokesperson declined to comment, while a Factorial spokesperson said that allegations were "without merit" and a thorough probe will absolve it. As per the SEBI order investment banking team of Credit Suisse had contacted Factorial in relation to the OFS of L&T Finance. (SEBI widens probe in L&T Finance insider trading case)

- LTFH is a financial holding company offering a diverse range of financial products and services across the corporate, retail and infrastructure finance sectors. The company also offers mutual fund products and investment management services, through their direct and indirect wholly-owned subsidiaries. The company is promoted by Larsen & Toubro Ltd.
- As per the Securities Contracts (Regulation) Rules, 1957 L&T the promoter was required to comply with the minimum public shareholding norms and reduce its shareholding in LTFH to 75% by August 2014.
- It is noted from the reply of L&T dated May 21, 2015 (Annexure 4 of the SCN) that in order to comply with the above, the Board of Directors of L&T at the meeting dated January 25, 2013 approved dilution

of the company's stake in LTFH either by way of OFS or through such other modes and authorized the management to take necessary actions. L&T reduced its shareholding by June 2014 vide the following modes :

- L&T disposed of 1% of its shareholding in LTFH on December 23, 2013 by way of market sale, after SEBI's approval.
 - L&T had to further offload a total of 6.46% shareholding in LTFH to bring its shareholding down to 75% after expiry of the requisite 12 weeks cooling-off period that was expiring on March 17, 2014.
 - L&T had earlier sought exemption from 12 weeks mandatory cooling-off period which was allowed by SEBI vide letter dated March 13, 2014.
 - L&T reduced its shareholding to an extent of 4.89% vide sale of 8,32,58,633 shares by L&T through OFS to the public on March 14, 2014
 - L&T further reduced its shareholding by a sale of 2,75,85,744 shares to Goldman Sachs (India) Securities Pvt. Ltd on June 11, 2014
- Price of the LTFH decreased from Rs.77.4 as on March 10, 2014 to Rs.74.30 as on March 14, 2014 during the investigation period. BSE Sensex decreased from an open of 21819.19 on March 10, 2014 to a close of 21809.8 on March 14, 2014.
- Price in the scrip decreased from Rs.77.5 as on March 10, 2014 to Rs.74.20 as on March 14, 2014 during the investigation period. CNX Nifty increased from an open of 6491.70 on March 10, 2014 to a close of 6504.20 on March 14, 2014.
- It is noted from the investigation that the price of LTFH scrip had declined sharply on March 13, 2014 on the day of introduction of scrip in the Futures segment and ahead of the announcement of OFS and its floor price. The price of the scrip opened on March 13, 2014 at Rs.86.6 and fell to close of Rs.79.2at BSE. After announcement of OFS and floor price, the scrip closed at Rs.74.3 on March 14, 2014 at BSE (Down 6.19% from previous day)
- It is noted that the announcement of sale of large stake by promoters affected the price of shares of LTFH in a negative way. In addition, the OFS at a significant discount to market price also impacted the price negatively. (SEBI)

Charges levied be SEBI

As is clearly evident that L&T Finance was guilty of insider trading and Rs.20,40,67,840 (Twenty Crore Four lakh Sixty Seven Thousand Eight Hundred and Forty only) being the amount of unlawful gains with simple interest @10% per annum from March 2014 till the date of payment.

Conclusion of the Study: As we see proving a party guilty of insider trading is not an easy task. A lot of hard work goes into it. As a lot of companies have indulged in this and have been found guilty, they must have used the loopholes in the guidelines of SEBI and the rulings of the Companies Act. So it really becomes important to curb insider trading as efficient functioning of the market is disrupted and leads to loss of money and faith of investors.

There have been a lot of laws protecting the interests of investors as we have seen how the laws came into being right from The Thomas Committee Report in 1948 to now SEBI becoming the watchdog of the financial markets. Every phase helped in overcoming the drawbacks of the previous laws which were being used by companies to help them in insider trading.

Although the new regulations of SEBI that came into being in 2015 appear to be very stringent and promising yet there has been quite a debate on the different meanings of particular phrases that have been used in the guidelines. Some examples are as under:

- In addition to listed companies, the new regulations apply to companies that are proposed to be listed. It is unclear what "proposed to be listed" means. Some believe it refers to companies which have filed the red herring prospectus but not registered yet but there is no clarity to it.

- The definition of “connected persons” covers everyone who has a connection with a company which is expected that the person will have insider information. These new regulations cover even public servants, who may not have any professional relationship with the company, but who may be aware of any policy which may affect the price of the share of the company.
- The new regulations require that the compliance officer of the company will have to monitor trading by employees and connected persons. But the wide scope of the definition of a “connected person”, it is a difficult task for the compliance officer.

As of now no such loopholes are visible which may be used by the companies in their favor for using inside information.

Also there is a debate over whether insider trading should be legalized or not to which I believe to some extent legalization is possible where it will not overlook the interests of the investors but would actually help as in the case of some negative information which is not usually given in the market and investors blindly trade in such securities. But where positive information is concerned it will hugely increase the prices of shares thus making the market unstable hence for such information it should not be legalized.

Also by legalizing to some extent will reduce the crimes committed as they will adhere to norms easily as it will benefit both the company and the investor.

Reference:

- (n.d.). Retrieved September 04, 2014, from Insider Trading Investopedia:
[/http://www.investopedia.com/terms/i/insidertrading.asp](http://www.investopedia.com/terms/i/insidertrading.asp)
- (n.d.). Retrieved September 4, 2014, from SEBI([Prohibition Of] Insider Trading) Regulations, 1992:
<http://www.sebi.gov.in/acts/insideregulation.pdf/>
- (n.d.). Retrieved from SEBI(Prohibition of Insider Trading) Regulations 2015:
<http://www.mondaq.com/india/x/438896/Securities/SEBI+Prohibition+Of+Insider+Trading+Regulations+2015>
- (1988). *Attorney General's Reference No.1*. India.
- SEBI Regulations, 1992*. (1992).
- Insider Trading, Investopedia*. (2014).
- Associates, N. D. (2014). *Insider Trading Regulations*.
- DLF Case summary*. (n.d.). Retrieved from India Corporate Law: <http://indiacorplaw.blogspot.in/2014/10/sebi-order-in-dlf-case-summary.html>
- KJHKHKJ. (9898, MHK 76). FHGFJHGFHKF. pp. 12-89.
- Sahu, S. D. (2015). *The Know All of Insider Trading-Decades of Corruptive prevention*. Law Octopus.
- SEBI*. (n.d.). Retrieved from SEBI Regulations:
http://www.sebi.gov.in/cms/sebi_data/attachdocs/1481256001818.pdf)
- SEBI widens probe in L&T Finance insider trading case*. (n.d.). Retrieved from Business Standard:
http://www.business-standard.com/article/markets/sebi-widens-probe-in-l-t-finance-insider-trading-case-114060600639_1.html